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The Platform for Sharing, Initiating and Learning Citizen Science in Europe

Deliverable 4.4

Report on the outcomes of the case study for the implementation of policy recommendations for citizen science

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Abstract	EU-Citizen.Science is an online platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources for citizen science. This document is the Deliverable 4.4 of the EU-Citizen.Science project. It describes the outcomes of the adoption of citizen science roadmaps and their impact in Spain, that is taken as a case study, due to its achievements in citizen science policies. The document provides a detailed approach to analyzing the state of the art of citizen science in a defined geographical area, in order to develop local and national plans that can improve citizen science practices, so that they can serve as an example for citizen science stakeholders and policymakers across Europe.
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Definitions and Acronyms

Action Plan	Action Plan for the Strengthening, Development and Consolidation of Citizen Science in Spain carried out by The Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology—Ministry of Science and Innovation and the Ibercivis Foundation
D	Deliverable
Data	Information, in particular facts or numbers, collected to be examined and considered as a basis for reasoning, discussion, or calculation. In a research context, examples of data include statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey

	results, interview recordings and images. The focus is on research data that is available in digital form. (European Commission, 2016)
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
EECTI 2021-27	Spanish Strategy for Science and Technology and Innovation 2021-2027 (In Spanish: <i>Estrategia Española de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación 2021-2027</i>)
FECYT	Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology —Ministry of Science and Innovation (In Spanish: <i>Fundación Española para la Ciencia y la Tecnología—Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación</i>)
FECYT Call	FECYT Call for Proposals for the Promotion of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Culture
H2020	Horizon 2020
Ibercivis	Ibercivis Foundation
MICINN	Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (In Spanish: <i>Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación</i>)
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
Observatory	Citizen Science Spanish Observatory project
Open Access	Access that is free to all and free of any licensing restrictions
Open Science	“The movement to make scientific research, data and dissemination accessible to all levels of an inquiring society.” (FOSTER Plus EU-funded Project)
R&D&I	Research, Development and Innovation

Repository	A location in which data is stored or managed
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
REDCC	Spanish Citizen Science Network (In Spanish: Red de Ciencia Ciudadana, REDCC)
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (United Nations)
SMART	Specific, Measurable, Assignable, Realistic and Time-bound
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

EU-Citizen.Science is an online platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources for citizen science. This document is the Deliverable 4.4 of the EU-Citizen.Science project. It describes the outcomes of the adoption of citizen science roadmaps and their impact in Spain, which is taken as a case study, due to its achievements in citizen science policies. The document provides a detailed approach to analyzing the state of the art of citizen science in a defined geographical area, in order to develop local and national plans that can improve citizen science practices, so that they can serve as an example for citizen science stakeholders and policymakers across Europe.

1 Introduction

1.1 Context, Purpose and Scope of this Report

EU-Citizen.Science is an online platform for sharing knowledge, tools, training and resources for citizen science – by the community, for the community. The aim of this project is to become the reference point for Citizen Science through cross-network knowledge sharing for citizen science participants, practitioners, researchers, policy makers and society across Europe.

The work plan of this project has assigned Work Package 4 (WP4) “Awareness and Engagement - Public and Policy Makers” the mission of demonstrating a conceptual model for awareness, empowerment and engagement in citizen science and for integrating citizen science across Europe. To achieve this, three main tasks were established: Task 4.1 ‘Achieving societal awareness and engagement in science through existing citizen science networks, projects and multiplier events’; Task 4.2 ‘General policy recommendations for citizen science’ and Task 4.3 ‘A case study for the implementation of policy recommendations for citizen science’.

After the submission of the Deliverable 4.1 *Guidelines and Recommendations Based on a Range of Best Practices for Achieving Societal and Policymaker Engagement* (Latham and Ceccaroni, 2020), much information and resources are now available on the Eu-Citizen.Science platform, offering relevant scientific evidence and best-practice examples to increase engagement with citizen science amongst identified stakeholders across Europe. It is important to note that government support seems to be a key factor in the success of citizen science projects, as Turbé et al. (2019) conclude, and, for this reason, two of the main tasks of WP4 focus on this specific stakeholder sector.

The purpose of this document, titled *Report on the outcomes of the case study for the implementation of policy recommendations for citizen science*, which is deliverable 4.4 (D4.4) of WP4, is to provide a description of the outcomes of the adoption of citizen science roadmaps and their related impact in Spain.

According to Flecha et al. (2018), it is important to include success stories in the public conversation, adding value to the best practices. Hence a successful action can be understood as not only that it has achieved its objectives, but also that it has an evidence-based impact on society and is able to be sustained over time, as well as to be replicated.

This D4.4 provides a detailed approach and a feasible methodology to analyse the state of the art of citizen science in a defined geographical area, in order to develop local and national plans so that citizen science can be taken as a reference, extrapolated or even replicated in different European contexts and in the respect of [EU-Citizen.Science values](#).

The case study described in this Deliverable has been framed and analysed by the Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT) and the Ibercivis Foundation (Ibercivis). Both

Foundations strongly believe in the importance of strengthening and communicating citizen science actions to attract more participants in collaborative scientific processes, and turn citizen science as a widely accepted and supported methodology.

Specifically, Spain is taken as a case study to analyse the implementation of policy recommendations for citizen science. Spain was one of the first European countries to support and expand citizen science, from 2012 when the term was first gaining global recognition (Liu et al., 2021). It is also the country where, in the last **five years - which is the timeframe of this study** -, several strategies and policies have been proposed, and even implemented, based on studies and experiences of citizen science practitioners.

In this Deliverable the “Spanish Citizen Science journey” is shown as a success story for promoting citizen science from the society and local entities to government and public administration; from citizens to policymakers. This document does not focus on specific local actions or projects, such as the successful practices carried out by the [Citizen Science Office of the Barcelona City Council](#) or the [D-NOSES](#) project, but reflects on three major points:

- Whether the experience of Spain over the last five years in citizen science, as well as its administration, is valid enough when it comes to strengthening and sustaining the citizen science carried throughout a country. In addition, the presence of Spain at the European level and its participation in EU-Citizen.Science through the MICINN-FECYT-Ibercivis node is also evaluated.
- Whether and to what extent the drawn conclusions may be due to a given, concrete context in the delimited time-space and whether the causalities identified can occur in other European contexts.
- Whether dialogue approaches between citizen science and policy (e.g., top-down and bottom-up perspectives, citizen science for policies and policies for citizen science, etc.) require a broader understanding and multidisciplinary analysis.

1.2 Precedents

This report has been written and edited by members of the Spanish node of the EU-Citizen.Science project: The Spanish Foundation for Science and Technology—Ministry of Science and Innovation (FECYT—MICINN) and Ibercivis.

FECYT is a public foundation established by a Council of Ministers Agreement in 2001 and attached to the Ministry of Science and Innovation (MICINN), which operates as a non-profit entity with functional autonomy. It was set up by the General State Administration to carry out activities related to the Ministry of Science and Innovation competences and other policymakers in the field of scientific and technical research, development and innovation.

According to its statutes, the mission of FECYT is to promote scientific research of excellence as well as the technological development and innovation necessary to increase the competitiveness of the Spanish industry and improve the quality of life of citizens, encouraging collaboration between agents and stakeholders involved in Research, Development and Innovation (R&D&I) activities and the dissemination and communication of its results. It also develops strategies to strengthen the links between science and society through actions that promote open-inclusive science, scientific culture and education, responding to the needs and challenges of the Spanish Science, Technology and Innovation System.

Since 2007, FECYT has been launching without interruption annual calls for proposals aimed primarily at agents of the Spanish science, technology and business system to carry out activities to promote scientific, technological and innovation culture, encouraging the bringing of science, technology and innovation closer to citizens, improving the scientific-technical education of society at all levels and promoting the active participation of society in R&D&I processes. More than 700 submissions have been received every year and 150-200 projects have been funded yearly with an average of €3,6M. In 2013 this call began citing supporting citizen science projects as a specific objective.

On the other hand, Ibercivis began its trajectory as a private non-profit foundation in 2011, thanks to the success of the distributed computing platforms Zivis and Ibercivis of the Institute of Biocomputing and Physics of Complex Systems–University of Zaragoza. This university as well as the Ministry of Economy, Industry and Competitiveness, the Government of Aragón, the Spanish Research Council and other Spanish public and private entities acted as founders.

Ibercivis aims to carry out, promote and make citizen science visible. Its experience as a distributed computing platform, in which they gave internet users the opportunity to donate computing cycles to scientific projects such as nuclear fusion, protein folding and material simulations, gave the foundation, the knowledge, capacity and skills to provide everyone with technical support, information and training to participate in scientific research, according to their interests and always dynamic capabilities. Since then, Ibercivis has led, promoted and/or supported citizen science projects at local, national and international levels. It also supports scientific agents by promoting local, national and international research in various areas of knowledge.

Thanks to the specific citation “Encourage citizen participation in the scientific process through citizen science activities” in the FECYT Call for Proposals for The Scientific and Innovation Culture Programme 2013, FECYT explicitly stated its financial support for citizen science projects. The activities should be carried out in part or in whole by non-scientists, by people who are not professionally engaged in science, through activities which may include data collection or data analysis”. Several Ibercivis projects were funded by this Call, initiating a relationship between the two foundations in the field of citizen science that has continued to this day.

2. Citizen Science in Spain: The Observatory

First of all, in order to understand this case study, it is important to explore the current situation of citizen science in Spain, a work that is carried out year after year by the [Citizen Science Spanish Observatory](#) (Observatory). This is an Ibercivis project co-founded by FECYT, which started in 2016. The Observatory functions as a repository of citizen science projects, contents and resources, a catalogue of citizen science practices, dissemination and science education information as well as quantitative analysis of the different dimensions of citizen science. It has the following objectives:

- Increase knowledge and attitudes towards citizen science.
- Give visibility to projects to facilitate participation and to disseminate their objectives and results.
- Identify the actors (research groups, funding programmes, citizen initiatives, physical spaces, NGOs...), collect the impacts of the different projects, promote the adoption of best practices, and lay the foundations for a continuous monitoring of citizen science in Spain over time.
- Facilitate coordination, synergies and collaboration between projects, and share resources and methodologies in the different fields of scientific research.
- Understand the influence of citizen science on scientific culture.
- Study how citizen science as a scientific methodology is changing the relationship between science and society as a whole, through the diverse practice of citizen participation in research.

From the beginning, a total of **316 initiatives** (of which 45 are from the last period, from December 2020 to september 2021), are linked on the Observatory web platform. To do this each initiative has filled up a form indicating, among other things, areas of knowledge and impacts achieved. Each of these initiatives can select one or several areas of knowledge when registering on the platform (**Fig. 1**).

Figure 1. Number of knowledge areas of the initiatives linked on the Observatory website.

As it can be seen in the graph above, more than half of the initiatives indicate Ecology and Environment (164 projects) as one of their areas of knowledge (multiple selection). The other most rated knowledge areas indicated are Biodiversity (153 projects), Social Sciences (88 projects) and Informatics and Computer Science (87 projects). Another result of this analysis is that the vast majority of projects are multidisciplinary (addressing two or more knowledge areas).

The Figure 2, displayed below, shows that the initiatives indicate (multiple selection) that they reach not only scientific impact. In fact, the number of projects with educational impact (136) exceeds the number of projects with scientific impact (132).

Figure 2. Impacts of citizen science initiatives hosted by the Observatory.

The graph below (**Fig. 3**) shows a relative equilibrium between projects according to the number of participants, with projects with a very small or very large number of participants being less frequent.

Figure 3. Percentage of initiatives by number of participants in the Observatory.

With regard to the recommended age of participation, there is a clear predominance of the option "all audiences".

Figure 4. Percentage of initiatives by recommended age of participation.

The Observatory also analyzes the status of citizen science in Spain at different levels: national/European/international. Below are reported some of the milestones achieved during the period: December 2020 to September 2021.

- The FECYT Call for proposals included citizen science among its lines of action (more information about this is reported in **Chapter 3.4**).
- Citizen science in Spain, whis is increasingly diverse in terms of topics, methodologies, scope and inclusiveness, generates relevant social, environmental and educational impact, in addition to scientific impact.
- Governmental entities such as the MICINN or the Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge, and public sector Foundations, such as FECYT, or the Biodiversity Foundation are promoting a wide range of citizen science projects that seek to provide answers (or have been providing them for years) to current global and local challenges. They are also aligned with the United Nation Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

- The MICINN, FECYT and Ibercivis, with the collaboration of the Ministries of Portugal and Germany and the European Commission through the EU-funded project EU-Citizen.Science, organized the first European high-level policy event to address citizen science with political representatives (more information about this is reported in **Chapter 4**).

Spanish citizen science in the European and international context

- Out of the **19 new citizen science projects with Spanish participation** funded by the latest Horizon2020 calls, **7 are led** by Spanish institutions.
- The 31 Spanish entities participating in these 19 new projects include 16 research organisations, 10 companies and 5 public administration entities.
- Projects have been funded both in the transversal line "Science with and for Society" of Horizon2020 and in the areas of "Societal Challenges", "Excellent Science" and "Industrial Leadership".
- The 19 projects (participated by 229 European partners) are funded for a total of €58,566,853.80 by the European Union. The 34 Spanish partners will receive €10,907,417.65 (18.6% of the total).
- EU support for citizen science can be foreseen in an increasing number of research areas, in particular in topics aligned with the Horizon Europe Missions and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

3. Action Plan for the Strengthening, Development and Consolidation of Citizen Science in Spain

The [SOCIENTIZE project](#) published the *White Paper on Citizen Science* in 2014 proposing a number of models for public participation: resources, experimental data collection, scientific data analysis tasks, participation in experimental games to analyse human behaviour, participation in physical spaces and collective intelligence experiments.

Among the recommendations in the *White Paper* there are proposals for policy makers to improve the integration of the general public in science through shared roadmaps at European, national and regional level. Within this context, in 2017, the Directorate General for R&D&I Policies of the Secretary of State for Research and Development tasked FECYT with drawing up an action plan for citizen science in Spain with the collaboration of experts in the field.

A working group of 15-20 experts representing different citizen science influential communities got involved to define the action plan through online questionnaires, virtual working sessions and other remote working methods, complemented by three face-to-face meetings. They were representatives of entities that were considered active in issues related to citizen science: Ministries, public and private science foundations, research centres, museums, universities, schools, science and social-environmental associations, cultural centres, makerspaces, citizen labs and Media.

The ‘Action Plan Strengthening, Development and Consolidation of Citizen Science in Spain’, that was finally signed in 2018, was coordinated by FECYT–Ibercivis and had the following specific objectives:

- Foster the development of a future Citizen Science Network in Spain that promotes the joint work of the actors involved and the representation of Spanish citizen science in international networks.
- Attract new actors to the Citizen Science Network in Spain, especially civil and social entities and researchers and research centres.
- Organise meetings on citizen science in Spain and Europe as well as a forum for national and international debate.
- Improve awareness of citizen science among scientific, environmental and social associations and social network users, which are the groups that may be most interested in participating in citizen science activities.
- Generate reusable communication materials to raise awareness of citizen science among the Spanish population.

These objectives were combined in three main activities,

- **Activity 1.** Development of the future Citizen Science Network in Spain.
- **Activity 2.** International Citizen Science Forum.
- **Activity 3.** Design of a communication plan to make citizen science known to target audiences.

From the signing of the agreement between Ibercivis and FECYT and until its completion on 31 March 2019, both entities worked intensively developing each of the above actions, giving rise to a strong boost to citizen science at the national level.

This action plan is the cornerstone on which the outcomes of this case study are based. The results presented in the next chapters are largely due to this commitment from policymakers to citizen science practitioners, and vice versa, to strengthen citizen science in Spain.

3.1 Activity 1: Development of the future Citizen Science Network in Spain

As established in the agreement, the first activity refers to the development of the future Citizen Science Network in Spain (REDCC). This network emerged from the five working meetings held with more than 100 participants in different cities. The thematic areas were agreed by FECYT and Ibercivis according to the strategic lines of science policies and the number of ongoing projects on each theme detected from the Observatory. The meetings were recorded in the minutes for subsequent analysis of its ideas.

Meeting 1: Heritage, Environment, Biodiversity and Citizen Science

The first of the thematic meetings was held on Wednesday 17 October in Seville in collaboration with the Descubre Foundation and was attended by 24 CC experts. The venue of the meeting was La Casa de la Ciencia - CSIC.

Picture 1. Working groups in Seville (2018).

Meeting 2: Astronomy and Citizen Science

This second meeting was held on Saturday 2 November 2018 in Cuenca in collaboration with the Agrupación Astronómica de Cuenca AstroCuenca and was attended by 24 CC experts. The venue for the meeting was the Museo de las Ciencias de Castilla-La Mancha. The meeting was held as part of the XXIII edition of the Congreso Estatal de Astronomía (CEA)

Picture 2. Working group in Cuenca and Conference on citizen science and astronomy (2018).

Meeting 3: Maker World and Citizen Science

The third meeting was held on Monday 10 December 2018 in Zaragoza in collaboration with the Zaragoza Knowledge Foundation and Etopia-Center of Art and Technology.. It was attended by 35 experts in CC and representatives of the maker community.

Picture 3. Presentation session and working groups in Zaragoza (2018).

Meeting 4: Communication and Citizen Science

This fourth meeting was held in Madrid on 21 January 2019 in collaboration with MediaLab Prado, which hosted the meeting. It was attended by 35 experts in CC and communication.

Picture 4. Presentation session and one of the working groups in Madrid (2019).

Meeting 5: City, Citizen Science and Recapitulation

The fifth and final thematic meeting was held in Barcelona on 8 February 2019 in collaboration with OpenSystems UB and was attended by 37 experts. The meeting was held at the Fàbrica de creació Fabra i Coats, in Barcelona and was attended by 37 experts in CC.

Picture 5. Coffee break and working groups in Barcelona (2019).

These meetings were designed as working sessions around two key issues. Firstly, what is the role and what are the needs in citizen science in that thematic area, trying to identify **SMART (Specific, Measurable, Assignable, Realistic and Time-bound)** actions that could positively and

substantially influence citizen science in that knowledge area. Secondly, to define a series of priority characteristics of the REDCC, in relation to (but not limited to) the following issues:

- Establishing the **objectives** of the network and, in particular, the specific objectives in the thematic area to be addressed by the meeting.
- Defining the **services** of the network.
- Defining the **obligations** and rights of network members.
- Define **membership** criteria and relevant aspects (quotas - voice/vote...).
- Establish an initial list of **working groups**.

At each of the meetings, citizen science projects related to the thematic area of the meeting were presented. These presentations served as a starting point to establish the necessary context, favouring the subsequent debate. Prior to each of the meetings, participants were provided with relevant documentation for an optimal development of the day.

In the following tables we are presenting the main actions to be done which emerged from each session. These actions are ordered by weight from 0 (less important) to 100 (more important). This weight was calculated using the allourideas tool, and represents the probability of one action to be chosen against one of the rest.

Meeting 1: Heritage, Environment, Biodiversity and Citizen Science

Table 1. Outcomes of Meeting 1 ordered by weight.

#	Action	Weight
1	Propose the criterion of citizen participation in the evaluation of projects co-funded by FECYT.	86
2	Create a common app that facilitates citizens' entry to participate in different projects.	77
3	Create a guide for good communication practices in citizen science.	68
4	Make a recommendation to the Conference of Spanish Universities Rectors, CRUE, on grants for citizen participation in projects.	62
5	Introduce the idea of citizen science in education to reach out to students, teachers and families.	60
6	Visibilise and publicise citizen science projects through promotional campaigns, public presentations, etc.	60
7	Take advantage of all existing forums related to scientific culture to disseminate the concept of citizen science.	57

8	Define a transparent management of both the projects and the REDCC itself.	56
9	Disseminate and take into account the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) 10 principles of citizen science in the implementation of projects.	56
10	Contact associations and entities to present projects related to their thematic areas.	55

Meeting 2: Astronomy and Citizen Science

Table 2. Outcomes of Meeting 2 ordered by weight.

#	Action	Weight
1	Create a list of resources for Astronomy hobbyist and citizen scientists.	73
2	Create physical spaces for the co-creation of projects with advice from those with experience (e.g. MediaLab, Zaragoza citizen labs).	70
3	Include on the Observatory's website the possibility for a person interested in a topic to find projects to join.	70
4	Create a knowledge network to start out in the field	66
5	Design a plan to make research centres aware of the potential of citizen science.	66
6	Prepare a way in which scientific entities can lend infrastructures to amateurs.	62
7	Collect successful results of citizen science (scientific impact, social impact, etc.).	61
8	Create a communication plan for citizen science at a general level, as well as communication guidelines at project level.	58
9	Create a code of good practice for citizen science.	56
10	Encourage the creation of citizen science projects covering the whole scientific process.	55

Meeting 3: Maker World and Citizen Science

Table 3. Outcomes of Meeting 3 ordered by weight.

#	Action	Weight
1	Hold a national citizen science maker activity and other maker events.	84
2	Establish cooperation and support agreements between different makerspaces and university/institute FabLabs.	81
3	Launch a call for three projects that can be replicated in different FabLabs and analyse results, such as the influence of space location.	69
4	Encourage projects to be inclusive: establish levels of participation so that anyone can get involved.	67
5	Have an accessible web platform with reliable information on resources, spaces, success stories, reference points, and people with competences.	65
6	Create a web platform for the maker movement that practice citizen science.	64
7	Ask scientific institutions to support and endorse citizen science maker projects.	61
8	Encourage researchers and academics to visit FabLabs.	61
9	Promote maker projects that link humanities and science, or that combine science, music, archaeology, gastronomy...	61

Meeting 4: Communication and Citizen Science

The objective of this meeting was not to obtain a set of actions to be implemented but to co-create a communication plan for citizen science projects (more information about this is reported in **Chapter 3.3**).

Meeting 5: City, Citizen Science and Recapitulation

This conference served to validate the proposals of previous conferences and to advance in the development of the REDCC. Particularly valuable was the contribution of Eva Méndez, from University Carlos III of Madrid, who identified the recommendations proposed in six main axes:

- **Axis I.** The promotion and recognition of citizen science practices.
- **Axis II.** The systematisation of information related to citizen science on a website (projects, people, good practices, repository of projects, social networks, identification/inventory of makerspaces-FabLab).

- **Axis III.** The creation of calls for citizen science projects including concepts such as multidisciplinary, multi-institutionality, etc.
- **Axis IV.** The dissemination of citizen science and the encouragement to include this methodology among researchers.
- **Axis V.** Data standardisation to allow interoperability between projects.
- **Axis VI.** Research on ethical aspects of REDCC (authorship, acknowledgement, exploitation of results, etc.).

Conclusions of the meetings

There were shared and specific needs depending on the thematic areas of the projects, but they were mainly related to governance (including political aspects, alliances, etc.), education, communication, ethical issues, data management and the need to embark on a common project.

In terms of citizen science approaches, two main groups of projects stood out, depending on whether they take a top-down (political/scientific authorities that approach to society) or bottom-up (society to political/scientific authorities) actions, both of which are perfectly valid. In the first case, the experts of the meeting considered that citizen science projects are more localised, being a type of citizen science closer to academic science, in the sense that its results are made visible in a very similar way to those of conventional science. Bottom-up approaches, on the other hand, can help to blur the dialogical barriers between science and society, increasing the impact of science and citizens' trust in scientific evidence.

Proposal for the future direction of the REDCC Network

During these five working sessions, and after studying the suggestions collected at the meetings, it became clear that there was a need to work on shared tasks in order to optimise work, facilitate replicability, establish intra-institutional and inter-institutional cooperation and synergies with society as a whole.

Therefore, the REDCC Network proposed to establish the following working groups. These working groups (WG) should be coordinated with other external ones, such as, for example, those of the ECSA) to operate as a Citizen Science Network in Spain;

- **WG1:** Governance in Citizen Science
- **WG2:** Education and Citizen Science
- **WG3:** Citizen Science Communication
- **WG4:** Ethics and Citizen Science
- **WG5:** Data Management in Citizen Science and Artificial Intelligence
- **WG6:** Execution of a shared Citizen Science project

Although the meetings served to establish synergies between the different citizen science actors, the constitution of the network as an independent unit with its own budget and legal and economic mechanisms to sustain the activities of the WG is still pending.

3.2 Activity 2: International Forum on Citizen Science

The [International Forum on Citizen Science in Spain](#) was held on 21 and 22 March 2019 as a final activity within the action plan to strengthen citizen science in Spain. The organisation of the event by Ibercivis and FECYT counted on the collaboration of the Technical University of Madrid and Medialab Prado Madrid, which hosted the event.

Picture 6. Images from The International Forum on Citizen Science in Medialab Prado (Madrid, 2019)

The two-day event brought together **135 participants** (project leaders, citizen scientists and representatives of various institutions and communities) to raise awareness of the many different forms and implications of citizen science as a scientific methodology that continues to spread in various parts of the world and, in particular, in Spain.

The Forum was organised as a meeting open to society as a whole to showcase the various practical possibilities and different visions when it comes to citizen science. Three plenary lectures were given by Jennifer Lynn Shirk, Karen Purcell (both from the Cornell Lab of Ornithology) and Caren Cooper (North Carolina State University) international references in citizen science. Initiatives promoted at the national level on different areas of knowledge and levels of involvement were presented. The forum closed with a round table, "You are not alone, networked citizen science", with Francisco Sanz, Executive Director of the Ibercivis Foundation; Paloma Domingo, Director General of FECYT and Teresa Riesgo, Director General of R&D&I in MICINN.

A total of 42 speakers took part in the different formats of the event (plenary talks, 20-minute talks, 8-minute talks and round tables). In addition, a stand area was set up where citizen science projects were presented. Several citizen science project workshops open to the general public were also held.

The event was an opportunity for a wide range of organisations and individuals to get in touch for the first time, or to learn more about both consolidated national and international projects

and recently initiated projects. The meeting was also an opportunity to listen to and get to know researchers who are national references, with a long track record in various fields of research. Several participants expressed the enormous usefulness of this type of meeting with concrete results in terms of establishing different types of cooperation between projects and/or institutions.

This meeting also sought to highlight the links between citizen science and the SDGs. It is widely accepted that successfully addressing these goals requires an educated and participatory citizenry. **SDG 17, which cuts across the other 16 goals, speaks of the need to build inclusive partnerships around shared principles and values, vision and goals that put people and planet at the centre. Precisely these alliances, manifested in interdisciplinary work or collaboration between professionals and amateurs, are fundamental axes in citizen science.**

3.3 Activity 3. Design of a communication plan to make citizen science known to target audiences

In a participatory process (scientific, socio-political and/or educational) it is important to **take into account the diversity of stakeholders involved and the channels and barriers to accessing them** (Llorente et al., 2021). Authors also remark that during the conceptualization phase of the project a strong focus on how it will be communicated to society in order to establish fruitful relationships must be present: “Communication can even be the basis for the effective performance of citizen participation projects focused on either deliberation (Ott and Knopf, 2019; Roberts, 2004) or science governance (Hagendijk and Irwin, 2006)”.

As Meeting 4 with science communicators reported, having a communication strategy also helps to take into account the language and message of human and social rights to vindicate citizen science not only as a provider of data but also as a creator of social change and more liveable societies, adopting the necessary ethical approaches to prevent opportunism and utilitarian attitudes that can arise in any activity involving citizen participation. Similarly, participants of this meeting suggested the need to eradicate discourses such as 'using citizens as sensors', recognising their/our autonomy and role as collaborators.

Before designing a successful communication plan to promote citizen science, it was necessary to do a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) analysis. This SWOT dissection showed how to better address the Action Plan, as can be seen in **Table 4**.

Table 4. Communication plan SWOT matrix

Strengths	Weaknesses
Strong sense of community among	Questioning the quality of data and results

participants Verified results Institutional support	provided by citizen scientists
Opportunities	Threats
Network of science communication and dissemination associations to collaborate with Support and synergies with various communities: journalistic and educational communities	Lack of involvement of some academic science institutions Difficulty for citizens to obtain results or analyze data

Based on this analysis, the following vision for the communication plan was established:

- Citizen science should be another **pillar to stand on when doing Science**, establishing connections and reducing the gap between professional science and society.
- Citizen science is a vehicle for creating a more scientifically **literate society** (*Science is learned by doing Science*).
- Citizens can contribute to **defining the direction of science** in Spain and its present and future research.

This aspiration laid bare the mission: To disseminate the work of citizen science, with the aim of finding a greater involvement of different communities as professional scientists, citizen scientists, journalists and/or policymakers. According to the following strategy:

1. To generate quality **content** on citizen science.
2. To achieve the maximum possible success and **dissemination** of the events carried out.
3. To expand the **community** of citizens and scientists interested in citizen science.

Unidirectional ways to communicate science have been present traditionally. Many authors agree that it is necessary to go beyond the “deficit model” and try other participatory approaches to have a two-way flow between science and the audience (Brossard and Lewenstein, 2010). The deficit model consists in attributing the lack of closeness and trust in science to the low level of knowledge.

As Llorente, Revuelta and Carrió (2021) confirmed, in Spain it is crucial to invest “extra effort” to identify the potential stakeholders and the approaching strategies, as well as valuing the level of commitment required in order to establish dialogical relationships with the audience. In this case study, it was important to define the different publics and the best way to connect with them:

- **Professional scientific community.** For this community, the communication strategy was aimed at presenting citizen science as a useful tool for them, for example, but not only, in data collection and analysis. Examples of successful projects were presented (some of

them concluding with a publication). The importance of using licences that are both conducive to research work and non-proprietary was also highlighted.

- **Community of citizen scientists.** Priority was given to recognising, making visible and thanking them for their scientific activity. Moreover, work was done to encourage them to present their own projects, without the need to be led, but supported, by an academic science framework. Within this community, the educational community has a special relevance.
- **Policymakers.** The key idea to communicate to the political community was to show examples where citizen science has been useful to create valid scientific results involving a large number of citizen scientists.

There were also actions to make the concept of citizen science known to society as a whole. They were directed not only through social media, but also in each of the thematic meetings, as well as in the International Forum workshops, which were open to the general public.

The communication plan was formalised in the following agreed and implemented actions during 2018-2019:

Table 5. Actions and Results of the Communication Plan (2018-2019).

Proposed action	Implementation
Dissemination	
Promotion and dissemination of the results of the 5 national events and the International Forum event through social media, press releases and articles on the Ibercivis, Observatory of Citizen Science in Spain and FECYT websites.	All the events and their results have been widely promoted through websites, social networks, press releases, etc.
5 videos of projects about citizen science and/or events 5 infographics of activities related to citizen science	7 videos have been published and are available at this link . 5 infographics have been designed: What is Citizen Science Maker World Astronomy Citizen Science and Society Citizen Science and SDGs They were disseminated on social networks and are available at the following link .
2 000 brochures and leaflets were designed and printed based on the above infographics.	2 000 brochures and leaflets were designed and printed based on the above infographics.

The programme of the International Forum is also included.	The programme of the International Forum is also included.
Social Media Impact	
1,000,000 impacts on social networks: Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, etc.	Achieved
Final report	
Creation of a final report summarising the tasks carried out and the impacts achieved, establishing recommendations for the future.	Achieved

3.4 Spanish Citizen Science Revitalisation: The Policies

The research done in the previous Meetings and with attendees of the International Forum points to the relevance of relying on political powers to promote citizen science. In fact, **there was a call for regulation that supports citizen scientists**: with funding, infrastructure, visibility, etc.

It was also suggested that it is important to foster, both from institutions and from citizen science projects themselves, a **culture of the relationship science-policy-society based on the concept of utility-service, cooperation and social inclusion**. Many participants highlighted the importance of seeking alliances between entities of all kinds (academia, business, foundations, associations, media...), fostering the capacity for communication and its benefits; also to find resources that are often unknown.

As a result of this analysis and the corresponding rethinking, various co-creation strategies were implemented in 2018-2019 to find solutions to the needs of citizen science practitioners, as well as to promote citizen science at the national level. These strategies converged three main actions:

- Public funding for the development of citizen science projects
- Spanish citizen science across Europe
- Long term sustainability strategies

Public funding for the development of citizen science projects

In the last ten years, there has been a change in attitude, both on the part of professional scientists and policy makers, from initial reticence to an understanding of the methodology of citizen science as beneficial and complementary to conventional science. This is why the

participants of the Meetings believed that **it was necessary to integrate the work of citizen science projects and that of the policymakers, establishing appropriate forms of cooperation between institutional science and citizen science.**

In the development of the meetings, special attention was paid to the involvement of policymakers in the discussion forums. Thanks to them and also to the conclusions drawn from these meetings, the benefits of the communication plan, the work developed by the Observatory and the high demand from citizen science practitioners for more funding, it was possible to wrap-up a final report and transfer the feedback to the MICINN, through FECYT and Ibercivis..

MICINN has been supporting citizen science in Spain through the FECYT Call for Proposals for the Promotion of Scientific, Technological and Innovation Culture since 2013. In 2018, and thanks in part to the importance that the recommendation of having specific funding had in the Meetings, MICINN-FECYT included a specific line of action for citizen science projects. This line was aligned with the *White Paper on Citizen Science for Europe* (2014) and it became an indicator of the growing importance that citizen science was acquiring in Spain and the value that from the MICINN was given to it.

The evaluation of applications to the FECYT Call is carried out by an evaluation committee formed by government representatives of Research and Technology and the direction of FECYT, in addition to independent experts of recognized experience in the dissemination and communication of science and technology. These evaluators prepare a scoring report for each project in which they evaluate:

1. The **objectives and quality** of the project.
2. The **innovation** and scientific-technical relevance of the project.
3. That the project is **structured and planned** realistically and correctly, sizing and adjusting the time, responsibilities, budget and resources to be used within the framework of the conditions and deadlines set by the call.
4. That the project encourages the **participation of new audiences (or including those who are being excluded)** usually distanced from scientific or technical environments.
5. Projects that have a strong **communication** strategy, experience of the team, as well as mechanisms to evaluate the impact of the project.

In the FECYT 2018 Call the citizen science line of action received 67 applications from all over the country and 18 projects were funded with a total of €300,000. Since then, another 114 applications have been received and 43 grants have been awarded, which adds up to a total of €660,000 of investment in citizen science by the Spanish Central Government. Many of the projects were selected to be part of the **catalogues of innovative and inspiring practices in Science Outreach** published every year by FECYT, indicating the fruitful current state of citizen science in Spain and how it is given value and rewarded by the public administration.

The trend over the last few years in terms of the number of projects submitted has been increasing (the Call in 2020 received 21% more projects than the one in 2019), which has also

been reflected in the number of projects funded (25% more). It is also interesting to highlight that the topics of the most recently funded projects correspond to the areas of Ecology and Biodiversity (60%), Archaeology and rural recovery (15%), while the other 15% is distributed in other types of disciplines. This provides a map at national scale of what is being done excellently at the public level in citizen science and how. As a consequence, **the Call not only benefits the scientific and citizen science communities, but organises and brings together national citizen science initiatives in order to create and facilitate communication channels with policymakers, as well as awaken their interest in citizen science issues.**

Spanish citizen science in the European context

To a large extent because the Action Plan was starting to be implemented, the MICINN put an eye on citizen science as a unique opportunity to strengthen the links between science and society and to generate spaces of trust between the different interest groups. As the International Forum revealed, **citizen science initiatives and projects, and their potential impact, were growing rapidly in Spain and throughout Europe, but the participants had the feeling that citizen science in Europe was blurred.**

That was one of the reasons why EU-Citizen.Science was born in 2019 to “develop and maintain an innovative, collaborative online hub to act as the centrepiece for bringing together a vibrant European citizen science”, as the agreement quotes. For MICINN it was essential to work on this mission and to establish strategic alliances with Europe. The participation in EU-Citizen.Science of the Spanish Government, together with FECYT and Ibercivis, which have joined efforts in citizen science issues, as a Spanish node in this European project was a unique opportunity to:

- Make citizen science more visible and to point out the value of citizen science actions and initiatives in Spain.
- Develop the EU-Citizen.Science platform and link with activities in Spain.
- Raise awareness of the importance of citizen science among different interest groups and its connection to the SDGs.
- Develop communication and training materials.

Above all, the participation in the EU-Citizen.Science project was a unique opportunity to use the experience of the work carried out over the years by the three institutions and by all citizen science agents in Spain, so that **the Spanish case can serve as an inspiration and a case study in Europe.**

These results are currently visible, for example, in **the number of Spanish projects uploaded to the platform, 40, which represent 20.8% of the total** from all over the European countries (accessed on eu-citizen.science on 29 October 2021). In addition, EU-Citizen.Science and the ECSA ten principles of citizen science are now taken into account in FECYT Calls.

Long-term sustainability strategies

Citizen science is a genuine science methodology in expansion; and a better knowledge of the collaboration networks and their evolution, within and between research communities, can establish new cooperation strategies in Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI). In fact, according to the last Observatory report (2020), the number of researchers publishing papers on research carried out within citizen science activities or with citizen science as a research subject is increasing, almost 10,000 in Spain.

FECYT-Ibercivis collaboration, together with the work carried out by citizen science professionals led the MICINN to mention citizen science as an important topic in a Spanish State Plan for the first time in 2017. The latest **State Plan for Scientific and Technical Research and Innovation 2021-2023** published is divided into several programmes and sub-programmes. Specifically, the Sub-programme for Knowledge Transfer aims to promote actions that **eliminate the existing barriers between different scientific and non-scientific actors in the public and private spheres** and increase the capacity for dissemination and communication of R&D&I to society. Through this sub-programme, continuity is given to the actions included in the previous State Plan 2017-2020, which highlighted the importance of consolidating citizen participation projects and activities.

After that moment, 2017, the progress of the Action Plan and the advances in terms of government administration on citizen science led to the fact that the **Spanish Strategy for Science and Technology and Innovation 2021-2027** (EECTI 2021-27), which was published in September 2020, specifically mentions citizen science among its four basic principles to support national research and innovation: "The social and economic responsibility of R&D&I through the incorporation of citizen science and the application of co-creation and open access policies, as well as the alignment of R&D&I with social values, needs and expectations" (translated directly from EECTI 2021-27 pg. 24). Having citizen science among the EECTI 2021-27 four principles will guide the definition, planning and implementation of public R&D&I policies. Furthermore, in October 2021 the Government of Spain created the Monitoring Committee of the EECTI 2021-27, Technology and Innovation 2021-2027, which will include the representation of FECYT, among other institutions. This also reveals how citizen science has become more interesting for political actors and shows that citizen science is established as a way of doing science and a tool for knowledge transfer in Spain.

However, there is plenty of work to be done. According to the Observatory there are still barriers from the citizen science system itself due to reluctance towards the involvement of citizens, validity of data, etc. and even from society, due to lack of information, reward system, need for feedback, etc. That is why it is important to emphasize that **citizen science must be a tool not only for science, but also for decision-making and social progress**. Citizen science for the future, after all.

4. Citizen Science for Policy across Europe

Although this case study is presented in this Deliverable as an isolated case, it is necessary to **put the Spanish citizen science state of the art in context with the rest of European countries**. This need was brought to the attention of the EU-Citizen.Science Consortium members and so it was decided to organise an event to share knowledge, experiences and specific examples across Europe and evaluate the replicability of the Spanish case study.

On June 22nd 2021, the EU-Citizen.Science project, FECYT and Ibercivis organized the policy event “[Citizen Science for Policy across Europe](#)” as a satellite event of the [European Research and Innovation Days 2021](#). This event was organized with the support of the European Commission, the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, the Portuguese Ministry of Science and Technology and Higher Education and the German Federal Ministry of Education and Research.

Representatives from ministries across Europe and at the regional and local levels were invited to engage in a discussion about citizen science and its benefits for policy making and to develop collaboration among policy makers with citizen science interests.

The main objectives of the event were:

- Explore the current state of citizen science in Europe to enhance synergies across borders.
- Open discussions by presenting good practices and success stories about citizen science operating at different levels, highlighting the barriers that affect the development of citizen science and providing solutions to overcome them to produce a powerful policy decision making tool.
- Foster collaboration among different countries to promote citizen science, establishing common paths.

The event was composed of four thematic blocks (**Fig. 5**) dedicated to discuss a citizen science topic: from barriers to citizen science, instruments to sustain activities and citizen science national plans, to the broad view of the European Commission. Each block began with a presentation given by an invited speaker, followed by an open discussion for sharing different experiences from representatives of the European Commission, Ministries of the European Member States and the participants in the event.

<h2 style="text-align: center;">Event Schedule</h2>	
11:00 - 11:05	Welcoming and introduction to the event by the EU-Citizen.Science Project coordinator and FECYT/Ibercivis.
11:05 - 11:25	Block 1: Current state of citizen science across Europe introduced by Sven Schade, Scientific Policy Officer, Joint Research Center, European Commission , followed by a discussion.
11:25 - 11:45	Block 2: Promoting citizen science through the launch of national plans for funding citizen science projects introduced by Carmen Castresana, General Director of Research Planning, Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation , followed by a discussion.
11:45 - 12:05	Block 3: Overcoming the barriers to citizen science introduced by José Paulo Esperança, Vice-President of the Foundation for Science and Technology, Portuguese Ministry of Science and Technology and Higher Education , followed by a discussion.
12:05 - 12:25	Block 4: Science for the people, by the people – policy instruments to anchor citizen science in research and society introduced by Anne Overbeck, Policy Officer for Citizen Science, German Federal Ministry of Education and Research , followed by a discussion.
12:25 - 12:30	Concluding remarks by the EU-Citizen.Science Project coordinator and FECYT/Ibercivis.

Figure 5. *Citizen Science for Policy across Europe* event agenda.

Detailed information about this event and its outcomes, in the form of a brief policy report, is available at eu-citizen.science.

After the end of the event, a survey was distributed among the event participants to get further feedback on the role of citizen science for policy making. The results of the survey are included in the above-mentioned brief report.

This event was an exceptional opportunity to take advantage of the knowledge shared in society through social and policymakers contributions. It also stressed the importance of approaching citizen science from different perspectives, showing the vision of policymakers from different countries.

As the ideas that emerged from the discussions at the event revealed, it is difficult to establish criteria for assessing the replicability of the case study in the European context, but the meeting demonstrated an interest in promoting the results of the EU-Citizen.Science project and helped to establish new synergies to work together and help other countries in Europe in establishing their own calls for projects, national plans and other policies to support citizen science. It is also important, as this report has shown, to take into account, among other things, the different socio-cultural factors influencing the communities in which we want to promote citizen science (Llorente et al., 2021).

5. Conclusions

This deliverable is a brief overview of the steps that have been taken in Spain to promote citizen science at national level. Obviously, the steps described here will have to be adapted before they can be applied to other contexts.

It is important to note that the Action Plan to strengthen, develop and consolidate citizen science in Spain described in this document has been achieved thanks to two entities strongly consolidated in citizen science aspects. On the one hand, Ibercivis manages as part of its line of work the Citizen Science Spanish Observatory and leads and/or participates in numerous citizen science projects, some of them funded by the European Commission. FECYT, on the other hand, is a public foundation under the Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation, and facilitates communication channels between society and government. The collaboration between both entities did their best to implement, catalyze and transfer this mission at all levels

Talking about the promotion of citizen science on a national level, it is even more difficult to establish good, universally applicable advice. The idiosyncrasies of each country are different and it will not always be possible to establish the actions indicated in this report. It is important to take into account not only the heterogeneity of the society as a whole, but also the diversity of the different actors that need to be involved in the process: researchers (with very different backgrounds and positions), policymakers and politicians, citizens, the press, etc. However, a series of general recommendations may be useful in promoting citizen science at the national level:

1. This case study highlights the **importance of financial support** from governments and higher levels for the development of citizen science projects in order to promote their implementation as an additional way of generating scientific knowledge.
2. It is a good practice to **combine both bottom-up and top-down approaches**. Although it is not always easy to obtain high-level support (ministries, etc.), combining top-down and bottom-up approaches will reduce the time and effort needed to achieve projects goals.
3. It is important to keep up to date a **Repository of National Citizen Science Projects** that can be used as a showcase. This repository needs to reach different types of areas: scientific, educational, social, cultural, economic, political, etc. in order to hold different profiles. The EU-Citizen.Science platform is a good place to start building this repository.
4. It is worth organizing **National Citizen Science Events**. Working sessions within these events will allow establishing action plans with a list of next steps to be taken by the different actors to boost citizen science. Moreover, if high-level support has not yet been achieved, these meetings, if strategically planned, can be used to raise awareness and obtain this support.
5. Where possible, having a **coordinated National Citizen Science Communication Plan** can significantly boost citizen science at the national level and save resources. This plan

will need to take into account different target audiences: researchers, policymakers, citizen scientists, citizens, the press, etc.

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